

Average Momentum and Quantum Mechanics in Photon Refraction

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We have considered the link between one-dimensional photon refraction-reflection and quantum mechanics in a number of notes. Here, we first consider two dimensional refraction to establish the idea that $E=pc$ with $c^2=c/n^2$ and $p^2=n^2 p$ for p,c being vacuum values, means that p^2 really represents an average momentum value because c^2 represents an average. In other words, moving from a vacuum into a medium, n^2 (index of refraction), with atoms or molecules, there is much empty space (vacuum) for which the vacuum result, $E=pc$, holds. In other words, $p^2=n^2p$ represents an average value and is not what one would actually measure if in a tiny vacuum region between atoms or molecules. We argue that the idea of probability and averages already arises at this point. In Newtonian mechanics, one usually thinks of a force changing a speed which then remains constant if there are no further forces. Such is not the case for the refracting photon. We further note that $c^2=cn^2$ and $p^2=pn^2$ are properties of the medium and as such are not linked to the vacuum- n^2 interface. This interface, however, represents an orientation in space and is linked with Newtonian forces. The physical result is the change in the angle of the refracted ray for 2D refraction. There is also reflection. In other words, the full ray p^2 is equal to n^2p because of the medium. There are two types of interactions, one the interface and the other with the medium. The latter is statistical in nature. We suggest that it gives rise to quantum mechanics. A full description of the photon interacting with atoms/molecules would be given by $F(p,x)$, but on average this may be replaced with $F(p^2, x)$ which already contains an average in x . One may then consider creating a continuity of this average and its first derivative at the vacuum- n^2 interface, we suggest to obtain quantum mechanical values. Using p^2 already suggests an average in time, so including reflection and refraction terms in 1D reflection-refraction is in keeping with this statistical viewpoint.

Two Dimensional Refraction

The Lorentz invariant: $E^2 + p^2 = m^2 c^2$ leads to $E=pc$ for $m=0$ ((1))

((1)) is degenerate in E for $p^2=n^2p$ and $c^2=c/n^2$. This scenario appears in nature in a medium with an index of refraction of n^2 , but nowhere in ((1)) does one see that this is an average effect. We suggest that a medium with an index of refraction of n^2 contains molecules or atoms, but also much empty vacuum space. The photon equation which holds in the vacuum region is $E=pc$. There is no p^2 or c^2 in the vacuum. The notion of p^2 , c^2 is an average in the refraction situation. This, we suggest, means that one requires the notion of probabilities. We argue that full description of the photon motion in the region with n^2 would be described by a function:

$G(p, x)$ which would give rise to an average p^2 , c^2 for each x point, or a function $F(p^2,x)$ ((2))

$F(p^2,x)$ is an average picture for each x point. We suggest that this is relevant because classically $P(x)dx = dx/L$, where L is length, for free motion. In other words, the average scenario is one which includes the notion of x and hence x at the interface of the vacuum and n^2 region.

In Newtonian mechanics, a force changes velocity and p (momentum) and then it moves with these constant values if there are no further forces. Such is not the case for refraction. Continual interactions with atoms/molecules give rise to an average c^2 and p^2 . This is a probabilistic problem described by averages and not usual Newtonian mechanics. Newtonian mechanics, however, applies to the interface between the vacuum and the n^2 medium and is linked with reflection and a change in the beam angle with the y axis if the interface lies along the x axis.

The momentum of the beam, however, has nothing to do with the interface orientation or position. It is linked with the interactions with the atoms/molecules and so $p^2 = n^2 p$ and $c^2 = c/n^2$.

We thus suggest that a probabilistic $F(p^2, x)$ function should be part of the analysis of refraction-reflection. We also note that in quantum mechanics, describing the photon in n^2 with the wavefunction, $\exp(ip^2 x)$, means that one really uses an average. In the vacuum region between atoms/molecules, one really has $\exp(ipx)$. We also note that in quantum bound problem, one has various physical $\exp(ipx)$'s, but takes an average $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ such that one obtains an average kinetic energy: $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. This, we argue, is analogous.

One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

We consider the simpler case of 1D reflection-refraction, because one does not need to deal with an angle of refraction. Reflection exists because of Newtonian impulse at the vacuum- n^2 interface, but the second set of interactions with atoms/molecules suggests one must use a probabilistic scheme incorporating $F(p^2, x)$. We suggest that this function should be continuous at the x_0 interface point together with its derivative. A single photon either reflects or refracts (not both), but using p^2 already suggests a time average, so one continues along these lines and incorporates reflected and refracted terms in the same equation. Two equations are needed for two unknowns (linked with reflection and refraction), but continuity of $F(p^2, x)$ and its first derivative supply this. These two equations may then combine to create one classical equation of reflection-refraction probability, namely:

$$1 = P(\text{reflect}) + P(\text{refract}) \quad ((2))$$

The continuity equations are:

$$F(p, x) + F(-p, x) = F(p^2, x) \text{ evaluated at } x_0 \quad ((3a)) \text{ and}$$

$$dF(p, x)/dx + dF(-p, x)/dx = dF(p^2, x)/dx \text{ evaluated at } x_0 \quad ((3b))$$

((2)) shows mutual exclusiveness of reflection-refraction so there cannot be any $F(p, x)$, $F(-p, x)$ cross terms. One immediate way to obtain this exclusiveness is to have d/dx bring in p or $-p$ so that one has a difference of squares. This is a possible solution which corresponds with the quantum mechanical free particle result $\exp(ipx) = F(p, x)$.

We suggest, however, that at the root of this whole approach is the statistical nature of p_2 of the refracted photon which requires one to adopt a statistical viewpoint of this problem even before considering the statistical nature of reflection or refraction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory and that this basic statistics/probability exists in a refracted photon. (There is also the idea of a photon either refracting or reflecting and in previous notes we argued that this was the source of probability in the problem). It is probabilistic, but here we suggest that the root probability lies in the expression $p_2 = n_2 p$ and $c_2 = c/n_2$. In other words, p_2 and c_2 are only averages. In a medium with index of refraction, n_2 , there are atoms and molecules, but also much vacuum space in which $E = pc$. In fact, a measurement in such a space would not return p_2 , c_2 . These only exist as average notions, implying a statistical/probabilistic picture. Furthermore, we argue that such a description should involve a function of x and p_2 . In other words, x must be included because in reality one has different physical results in different x positions, but averages to use p_2 at each x . This suggests a function, $F(p_2, x)$. Newtonian mechanics only applies at the vacuum- n_2 interface and is linked with reflection and the angle of refraction. P_2 holds for the whole photon beam and is not linked to the position or orientation of the beam.

If one uses a simpler 1D, instead of 2D, reflection-refraction problem one may include reflected and refracted pieces together because p_2 already is a time average. One may then try to have continuity of $F(p, x)$ and its d/dx derivative at x_0 , the vacuum- n_2 junction, i.e. ((3a)) and ((3b)). This leads to $\exp(ipx)$ as a possible solution of $F(p, x)$ which represents free particle quantum mechanics. Thus, $\exp(ip_2 x)$, the free photon wavefunction, actually uses an average p_2 value. In vacuum regions between molecules one really has $\exp(ipx)$. A similar situation holds for a quantum bound system, showing that $\exp(ipx)$ and $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ are really related to a special kind of probability.